

XLMS: sample preparation, mass spectrometry and data analysis:

Samples were prepared in 75 mM NaCl, 10 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 1 mM DTT and crosslinked with BS3 (bis(sulfosuccinimidyl)suberate, Thermo Fisher A39266) at final concentration of 0.25, 0.4, 0.5, 0.75, and 1 mM for 45 min at 25°C, before quenching with 50-fold excess of 1 M Tris-HCl (pH 8.0). Proteins were separated using SDS-PAGE (200 V, Thermo Fisher NP0050, NP0335BOX) and stained with GelCode Blue (Thermo Fisher 24592). Supershifted bands were excised from the gel, destained twice with 100-fold (m/m) excess of 50% acetonitrile (ACN, Millipore Sigma 900667) in 25 mM LC-MS-grade ammonium bicarbonate (ABC, Honeywell Fluka, 40867), 37°C, 30 min, with agitation. Destained slices were replaced into 100 µl of 50 mM tris-2-carboxyethyl)phosphine (TCEP, Millipore Sigma, 646547), incubated for 10 min at 60°C, and destained as described above. Destained sliced were incubated in 100% ACN, and air dried for 10 min, before addition of 75 µl of 25 mM ABC, supplemented with 50 ng/µl of MS-grade trypsin (Thermo Fisher 90305) and 0.01% ProteaseMAX Surfactant (Promega, V2071). Digestion was carried out for 120 min at 54°C, peptides were collected as described in ProteaseMax application note (Promega, TB373, Rev. 2/15), and purified using Pierce C18 Spin Tips (Thermo Fisher PI84850). Peptide samples were dissolved in 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (FA, Thermo Fisher Scientific, LS118-4) for MS analysis. Peptides were analyzed in an Orbitrap Fusion Lumos mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) coupled to an EASY-nLC (Thermo Scientific) liquid chromatography system, with a 2 µm, 500 mm EASY-Spray column (Thermo Scientific, ES903). The peptides were loaded on the column in 100% buffer A (0.1% FA in water), and eluted at 200 nl/min over either linear 140 min gradient 4-40% buffer B (0.1 % FA in ACN, Thermo Scientific 85174), or 195 min concave gradient (4-30%, curve value set at 6). Each full MS scan (R = 60,000) was followed by 20 data-dependent MS2 (R = 15,000) with high-energy collisional dissociation and an isolation window of 2.0 m/z. The normalized collision energy was set to 30%. Notable selection algebra included 4-6 charge precursor isolation window, TopN, [lowest charge then most intense] operators. Monoisotopic precursor selection was enabled and the dynamic exclusion window was set to 30.0 s. Resulting raw files were searched in enumerative and cross-link discovery modes. Enumerative mode was engaged by applying open search implemented in the pFind3 software (Chi et al., 2018) using the fasta file combining sequences of the recombinant targets and the expression host proteome (*E. coli*, Uniprot UP000000625) as the search space. Fasta sequences of proteins identified in the samples in the enumerative mode were combined to form the search space for crosslink discovery by pLink2 (Chen et al., 2019); protein modifications inferred by pFind3 and comprising >0.5% of the total were included as the variable modifications in pLink2 search parameters. pLink2 results were filtered for FDR (<5%), e-value (<1.0E-3), score (<1.0E-2).

Chi, H., Liu, C., Yang, H., Zeng, W.F., Wu, L., Zhou, W.J., Wang, R.M., Niu, X.N., Ding, Y.H., Zhang, Y., et al. (2018). Comprehensive identification of peptides in tandem mass spectra using an efficient open search engine. *Nat Biotechnol.* 10.1038/nbt.4236.

Chen, Z.L., Meng, J.M., Cao, Y., Yin, J.L., Fang, R.Q., Fan, S.B., Liu, C., Zeng, W.F., Ding, Y.H., Tan, D., et al. (2019). A high-speed search engine pLink 2 with systematic evaluation for proteome-scale identification of cross-linked peptides. *Nature communications* 10, 3404. 10.1038/s41467-019-11337-z.